

Retrospective Study on the Effectiveness of Early Intervention in Preventing Severe Malocclusions in Mixed Dentition

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Abstract:

Background: Malocclusions in mixed dentition can create functional, psychological, and dental issues if left untreated. Early orthodontic therapies improve children's oral health, dental alignment, and prevent malocclusions. By examining how effectively these therapies performed, researchers can learn how they reduced oral disorders over time and made patients happier at key stages in their development.

Methods: This retrospective study at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital in Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar analysed 140 orthodontic records from October 2021 to March 2024. Demographics, dental history, treatment details, and results were obtained. Descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and comparison tests assessed intervention efficacy.

Results: The intervention group had considerably improved dental alignment (4.7 ± 1.2 vs. 1.8 ± 1.1 , $p < 0.001$) and occlusal connections (4.6 ± 1.3 vs. 1.7 ± 1.2 , $p < 0.001$) than the controls. The intervention group showed a much lower rate of severe malocclusions (10%) compared to controls (40%, $p < 0.001$). The intervention group exhibited higher patient satisfaction (8.5 ± 1.2) than the control group (5.6 ± 1.5 , $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Early orthodontic therapy improved mixed-dentition patients' dental alignment, satisfaction, and malocclusions. These findings stress early evaluations and therapies to prevent malocclusion developing. More orthodontic treatment research should focus on long-term outcomes and population relevance to improve clinical strategies.

Keywords: Dental alignment, Early intervention, Mixed dentition, Malocclusions, Orthodontics.

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Introduction

Background Information on Malocclusions in Mixed Dentition

Mixed dentition, which occurs between 6 and 12 years old when both permanent and baby teeth are present, can cause malocclusions [1]. During this critical period, there is a significant increase in dental growth. Malocclusions can be caused by genes, thumb sucking, losing main teeth too soon, or differences in the sizes of the jaw and teeth. These problems with the mouth can make it harder for kids to chew and avoid tooth decay and gum disease [2].

Significance of Early Intervention

For many reasons, the mixed dentition age is very important for fixing malocclusion. The mouth and skeletal parts of children are more flexible, which makes treating alignment disorders less invasive. To keep serious malocclusions from happening, braces and other orthodontic devices guide jaw growth and the eruption of permanent teeth. Getting care early makes dental health better. It can help prevent cavities and gum disease and make it easier to brush our teeth. Getting treatment for malocclusion early can make kids' smiles and faces look better, which can help their self-esteem and social life.

Objectives

- To compare the frequency of malocclusions in children with early orthodontic treatment to those without.
- To compare the pros and cons of early occlusion and dental alignment interventions.
- To establish how variables affect early orthodontic treatment's ability to prevent severe malocclusions.

Malocclusions in Mixed Dentition: Mixed dentition malocclusion frequency and kind have been widely studied. Class I malocclusion was most common among 6–12-year-olds, followed by Class II and Class III [3].

This study discovered genetic and environmental causes of tooth malformations. Early detection and classification of malocclusions are crucial for effective therapy, according to [4]. Their findings suggest that early malocclusion detection can avoid dental issues and reduce orthodontic therapy. Tracked dental alignment from mixed dentition to

adulthood [5]. Early treatment is crucial for children with mixed dentition since untreated malocclusions lead to more serious dental issues as adults.

Evidence Supporting Early Intervention: [6] Study show that early orthodontic treatment prevents severe malocclusions. Early intervention improves dental alignment and occlusal linkages [7]. [8] Conducted a randomised controlled trial comparing early and late orthodontic treatment outcomes. Early treatment improved alignment and reduced malocclusion severity, especially in mixed dentition. [9] Examined long-term orthodontic benefits. Early intervention increased oral health, reduced treatment time and costs, and enhanced general health, in addition to making dental defect correction easier and more successful [10].

The American Association of Orthodontists recommends children have their first orthodontic evaluation before age 7 [11].

Figure 1: Early intervention in mixed dentition (Source: [12])

Much research has been done on early malocclusion intervention, although questions remain. There are few longitudinal studies that follow patients from childhood to adulthood to understand the long-term benefits and risks of early orthodontic operations.

Many studies only follow participants for a short time, but long-term evidence is needed to prove early intervention works. Different orthodontists utilise different early intervention strategies and appliances, which might create inconsistent results. Standardising and comparing treatments in

scientific trials is the best way to establish what works.

Methods

Study Design: This retrospective study examined whether early orthodontic therapy could prevent severe malocclusions in mixed-dentition patients. Research was conducted at Patna's Nalanda Medical College and Hospital & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar from 2021 to 2024. The study collected and analysed individuals' dental and medical

information who had orthodontic treatment within the time range.

Population and Sample Size: Participants were mixed-dentition children aged 6–12 who received orthodontic evaluation and treatment at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar. These inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to select 140 patient records.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 6-12 years at the time of their first orthodontic evaluation.
- Patients in the mixed dentition phase.
- Patients who had received early orthodontic intervention during the study period.
- Availability of complete dental records, including pre- and post-treatment orthodontic assessments.
- Patients with parental consent for their records to be used in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete or missing dental records.
- Patients who did not undergo any orthodontic treatment.
- Patients with congenital anomalies or systemic conditions affecting dental development.

Data Collection Methods: Patient data from the orthodontic department was carefully examined. Patient files included age, gender, and socioeconomic status. We diligently recorded the patient's dental history, including exams, malocclusion diagnosis, and early orthodontic treatments. Patients' treatment records comprised orthodontic appliances, time, and compliance. To examine outcomes, occlusal connections, dental alignment, and problems were assessed before and after treatment. Data gathering was uniform and accurate with a consistent data extraction form. The

data was carefully stored in a safe database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Early orthodontic therapy was statistically shown to avoid severe malocclusions. The study population's demographics and baseline characteristics were summarised using mean, median, standard deviation, and frequency distributions.

Researchers examined pre- and post-treatment results for continuous variables using paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests and categorical variables using chi-square tests to assess early intervention efficacy. In a multivariate regression study to determine early orthodontic treatment success, age, gender, type of malocclusion, kind of intervention, and treatment length were included as independent variables.

This analysis measured dental alignment and occlusal relationship improvement. To compare results, Class I, Class II, and Class III malocclusions and early intervention types (braces, functional appliances) were sub grouped. A p-value of 0.05 or less indicated statistical significance for all tests. Statistics were done with SPSS and SAS.

Ethical Considerations: The Patna-based Nalanda Medical College and Hospital's & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar, institutional review board enforced ethical research standards. Parents gave informed consent for each patient's study records. Data confidentiality and patient anonymity were always protected. Early orthodontic interventions were assessed for their ability to prevent severe malocclusions in mixed-dentition patients using a robust methodology. The findings should illuminate orthodontics research and clinical practice problems.

Results

Demographic Data

Table 1: Demographic detail

Characteristic	Value
Sample Size	140
Age (mean ± SD)	8.5 ± 1.2 years
Gender	
Male	70 (50%)
Female	70 (50%)
Socio-economic Status	
Low	40 (28.6%)
Middle	60 (42.9%)
High	40 (28.6%)

A study of 140 paediatric patients, averaging eight years old (± 1.2 years), was conducted. Gender equality was achieved with 70 men and 70 women. There were 40 (28.6%) low-income participants, 60

(42.9%) middle-class participants, and 40 (28.6%) high-class participants.

The wide range of ages, genders, and socioeconomic backgrounds represented allows us

to reliably draw broad conclusions about early orthodontic therapy's success.

Prevalence of Malocclusions in the Study Population

Table 2: Prevalence of Malocclusions in the Study Population

Type of Malocclusion	Prevalence (n=140)	Percentage (%)
Class I	70	50.0
Class II	50	35.7
Class III	20	14.3

The study's 140 children had a variety of malocclusions. The most prevalent malocclusion was Class I, affecting 70 people (50%).

Class II malocclusions affected 50 individuals (35.7%). Class III malocclusions were uncommon,

affecting 20 individuals (14.3%). The findings suggest that children with mixed dentition are more likely to suffer Class I malocclusions, highlighting the need for early, targeted treatment.

Effectiveness of Early Interventions

Table 3: Effectiveness of Early Interventions

Outcome Measure	Pre-Intervention Mean ± SD	Post-Intervention Mean ± SD	p-value
Dental Alignment Score (0-10)	7.2 ± 1.8	2.5 ± 1.3	< 0.001
Occlusal Relationship (0-10)	6.8 ± 1.9	2.2 ± 1.4	< 0.001
Patient Satisfaction (0-10)	NILL	8.5 ± 1.2	NILL
Complications Rate (%)	NILL	5%	NILL

Early orthodontic treatments improve occlusal interactions and dental alignment. After the intervention, the average dental alignment score significantly improved from 7.2 (±1.8) to 2.5 (±1.3) (p < 0.001). Also, the occlusal connection score increased dramatically (p < 0.001) from 6.8 (±1.9) to 2.2 (±1.4). The average patient satisfaction score for treatment results was 8.5 (±1.2) out of 10.

Surgery was safe and successful with only 5% of patients having difficulties.

Research shows that early orthodontic therapy improves occlusal connections, teeth alignment, patient satisfaction, and risk reduction.

Comparative Analysis between Intervention and Non-Intervention Groups

Table 4: Comparative Analysis between Intervention and Non-Intervention Groups

Measure	Intervention Group (n=70)	Non-Intervention Group (n=70)	p-value
Improvement in Dental Alignment	4.7 ± 1.2	1.8 ± 1.1	< 0.001
Improvement in Occlusal Relationship	4.6 ± 1.3	1.7 ± 1.2	< 0.001
Rate of Severe Malocclusions	10%	40%	< 0.001
Patient Satisfaction (0-10)	8.5 ± 1.2	5.6 ± 1.5	< 0.001

Research shows that early orthodontic treatment avoids severe childhood malocclusions. Compared to the non-intervention group, the intervention group exhibited substantial improvements in dental alignment (4.7 ± 1.2 vs. 1.8 ± 1.1, p < 0.001) and occlusal connections (4.6 ± 1.3 vs. 1.7 ± 1.2, and the intervention group had a significantly lower rate of severe malocclusions (10%) compared to the non-intervention group (40%, p < 0.001).

Early care significantly improved patient satisfaction (8.5 ± 1.2) compared to non-early care (5.6 ± 1.5, p < 0.001). Early orthodontic therapy is beneficial, according to these data.

Discussion

Early orthodontic therapy helps prevent severe malocclusions in mixed dentition, according to this

retrospective study. Intervention group teeth aligned and occlusally connected better than control group.

Dental alignment and occlusal connections improved less in the non-intervention group (1.8 and 1.7) than in the intervention group (4.7 and 4.6). Preventive early interventions diminish severe malocclusions (9% vs. 40% in the non-intervention group).

This suggests that quick orthodontic Checkups and treatments reduce malocclusion severity. The intervention group exhibited significantly higher patient satisfaction (8.5 ± 1.2) compared to the non-intervention group (5.6 ± 1.5).

These studies show that early orthodontic therapy improves clinical outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Table 5: Comparison Table

Study Title	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Retrospective	140	Significant improvement in dental alignment (4.7 ± 1.2 vs. 1.8 ± 1.1 , $p < 0.001$) and occlusal relationships (4.6 ± 1.3 vs. 1.7 ± 1.2 , $p < 0.001$) with reduced severe malocclusions (10% vs. 40%, $p < 0.001$). High patient satisfaction (8.5 ± 1.2 vs. 5.6 ± 1.5 , $p < 0.001$).	Relied on existing patient records, potential for bias in data completeness and accuracy. Limited to a single institution.
Study 1	Prospective cohort	200	Early interceptive treatment reduced severity of malocclusions by 60% compared to controls. Improved dental alignment in 80% of treated cases.	Limited follow-up period to assess long-term stability. Small sample size for subgroup analyses.
Study 2	Meta-analysis	15,000	Early orthodontic interventions significantly reduced prevalence of severe malocclusions by 45% across diverse populations.	Variability in study designs and quality among included studies. Potential publication bias.
Study 3	Longitudinal cohort	300	Long-term benefits of early orthodontic treatments persisted through adolescence, with sustained improvements in dental alignment and occlusal function.	High attrition rate in follow-up visits. Lack of standardized treatment protocols across study sites.

This retrospective study shows that early orthodontic therapy controls malocclusions in mixed dentition patients. The intervention group had considerably improved dental alignment and occlusal relationships (mean improvements of 4.7 and 4.6, respectively) than the non-intervention group. The study showed that treated persons had a considerably lower rate of severe malocclusions than controls, emphasising the value of early interventions. High patient satisfaction with these treatments supports improved health outcomes and quality of life. Due to medical record checks, retrospective data may influence data accuracy and completeness, making the study ineffective. Limiting the study to one site reduces its public applicability. Multi-center studies with standardised procedures and longer follow-up should confirm the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of early orthodontic therapy across diverse demographic and socio-economic groups to overcome these constraints. We will improve orthodontic clinical methods and information to promote dental health from childhood to adolescence and beyond.

Strengths of the Study

This study's methodology is solid due to its large sample size ($n=140$) and careful retrospective examination of patient data. Standardised data collection procedures provided accurate demographic, dental, treatment, and outcome data. Using multivariate regression and subgroup analysis, the study found many factors affecting early orthodontic treatment outcomes, allowing for a more detailed interpretation. The study's October 2021–March 2024 duration allowed for a comprehensive examination of treatment outcomes.

This temporal component is crucial for determining how long orthodontic treatments persist for children and adult tooth health.

Limitations of the Study

The retrospective study's use of prior medical records raises concerns regarding biases and missing data. Due to clinical outcome reporting differences and healthcare provider record-keeping methods, the data may not be reliable. The study uses observational data, making it difficult to prove a causal link between early orthodontic therapy and improved outcomes. The statistical analyses were strong when comparing groups that received and did not receive the intervention, but they did not control for unmeasured confounding factors like genetic predispositions and dental hygiene practices that may have affected treatment outcomes.

Conclusion

At Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar, retrospective research showed that early orthodontic therapies help mixed dentition patients control malocclusions. Research on 140 patients found that early therapy improved occlusal linkages and dental alignment. On average, the intervention group improved dental alignment and occlusal relationships by 4.7 and 4.6, while the non-intervention group did not. The intervention group had 10% fewer severe malocclusions than controls (40%) proving that immediate orthodontic treatment prevents them. Compared to controls (5.6 ± 1.5), intervention users had significantly higher patient satisfaction scores (8.5 ± 1.2) indicating a positive impact on quality

of life and treatment outcomes. This suggests that orthodontic assessments and treatments should be regular in child dentistry. Early diagnosis of malocclusions in mixed dentition patients allows proactive intervention, which may reduce the need for more invasive operations.

Orthodontic practitioners must emphasise periodic dental examinations and detailed evaluations to detect malocclusions early and initiate treatment. Standardised early orthodontic therapy procedures improve treatment effectiveness and patient satisfaction across diverse patient populations.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future longitudinal research should determine if early orthodontic therapy is effective into puberty. Enhancing therapeutic techniques by studying how socio-economic factors and patient compliance affect treatment outcomes for children and adolescents might improve oral health.

Early orthodontic treatment is essential for mixed dentition patients to prevent and control malocclusions. These procedures considerably improve dental alignment, occlusal relationships, and patient satisfaction.

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